

Guidelines for modelling

CODECS Socio-technical process modelling

CNR

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Introduction

As part of CODECS Task 3.3 - Farm Socio-technical Process Modelling, this document presents the procedure for creating the process diagrams starting from the **Living Lab Reports**. This document is oriented to the task leaders' collaborators, who will check the consistency of the reports and create the diagrams.

The reports are the output of previous activities carried out by Living Lab coordinators, who performed data collection through interviews and group discussions involving the Living Lab participants and filled in the template file according to the guidelines provided.

The objective of the process modelling activity is to create easy-to-read diagrams of processes carried out in a farm before and after the introduction of digital solutions. The output of the activity will allow to focus on the transformation that occurred to a process after the introduction of a digital solution and will contribute to the cost-benefit analysis.

To ensure completeness, the following diagrams are developed, based on the data from the reports:

- the **goal diagram** models the goals of the process focusing on the intentional, social, and strategic dimensions;
- the **structure diagram** provides an overview of the entities, i.e., actors, tools, infrastructures, and systems involved in the process and the relationships among them;
- the **process diagrams** represent the detailed flow of the process and will allow comparisons between the process before and after the introduction of the digital solution.

The goal and the structure diagrams focus on the process *after* the introduction of digital technology (process *as-is*), whereas the process diagram focuses both on the process *after* (process *as-is*) and on the process *before* the introduction of the digital technology (process *as-is*).

A set of languages for graphical representation from software engineering has been identified, so the diagrams will be developed using the following notations: iStar, goal diagram; UML, structure diagram; BPMN, process diagrams.

To maximise the readability of the diagrams a small set of elements for each notation has been selected. Furthermore, the authors adopted a modified style for the iStar notation by

creating an enhanced version consisting of icons for representing actors and a different style for the symbols. This is to obtain more user-friendly representations.

Chapter 2 provides an explanation by example of the diagrams to be created. Chapter 3 contains hints on the software for creating the diagrams and provides access to three templates. Chapter 4 presents an overview of the contents to be extracted from the reports. Chapter 5 contains step-by-step instructions on how to create the diagrams.

Common terms

Actor – individuals, groups, or system components that play a role in the process;

Diagram – a visual representation of information, typically simplified and structured to convey a specific concept or set of relationships among components;

Focal Action Situation (FAS) – a situation where components of a socio-technical system interact to provide an outcome;

Goal – is a desired outcome or target that an actor or group of actors aims to achieve within a specific process or task;

Goal diagram – a type of diagram used to represent the actors' goals, relationships and dependencies within a process;

Living Lab (LL) – a network of farmers, knowledge intermediaries, stakeholders, policy makers, technology providers constituted around an emerging problem within a given application scenario and willing to develop solutions through collaboration;

Model – a simplified representation or abstraction of reality designed to explain, predict, or analyse aspects of the real world. Models can take various forms depending on their purpose and the field in which they are used;

Notation – a system of symbols, signs, or characters used to represent information in a concise and standardised way;

Problem statement – a concise description of an issue or challenge that needs to be addressed;

Process – a sequence of steps performed by actors to address an objective, for example, irrigation or cattle monitoring;

Process as-is – process *before* the introduction of a digital solution;

Process diagram – a type of diagram that illustrates the sequential tasks, interactions, or events from the beginning to the end of a process;

Process modelling – the act of creating a visual representation or abstraction of a process in order to understand, analyse, communicate, and improve it;

Process to-be – process *after* the introduction of a digital solution;

Resource – tangible and intangible) assets owned or accessed by the LL and utilised to create value, achieve an objective, or solve a problem;

Structure diagram – a type of diagram used to represent the structure of a process by illustrating its static aspects, such as actors, resources, composition, and arrangement of the system;

Task – a specific, defined activity that needs to be completed as part of a larger process;

Tech component – an individual part or element of a tech system. Each component has a specific function and contributes to the overall operation of the system;

Tech system – an interconnected set of hardware, software, data, and procedures designed to perform specific functions and achieve certain goals;

Diagrams

The process modelling methodology is based on a set of different diagrams leveraging on standard notations from software engineering.

According to the process modelling methodology, to ensure completeness of the process representation, the following diagrams are developed: (1) goal diagram - process *after*; (2) structure diagram - process *after*; (3) process diagram - process *before*; (4) process diagram - process *after*; (5) processes overlap.

This section introduces the different types of diagrams providing a legend and an explanation of the symbols used.

Goal diagram

The goal diagram models the goals of the process *after* focusing on the intentional, social, and strategic dimensions.

Figure 1: Example of a goal diagram

Figure 1 contains an example of a goal diagram for a Farm Management Information System in the context of a cheese production process. For this type of diagram, we adopt a modified style for the iStar notation by creating an enhanced version consisting of icons for representing actors and a different style for the symbols.

The complete case study can be downloaded here: [iStar goal diagram](#)

Legend

Figure 2: Legend of symbols used (on the left); portion of diagram with types of goals highlighted (on the right).

Explanation of symbols

Actor: an active, autonomous entity that performs tasks by exercising its know-how, in collaboration with other actors;

Actor boundary: contains all tasks, goals and resources/tools related to a single actor;

Technology boundary: same as actor boundary but with no goals associated;

Task: represents an action that an actor wants to be executed;

Resource/tool: a physical or informational entity that actors require to perform tasks

Goal: a state of affairs that the actor wants to achieve;

Types of goals

Internal goals: actor's goals within its activity/role;

Actor-actor goals: actor's goals with respect to other actors;

Actor-technology goals: actor's goals with respect to digital technology

Structure diagram

The structure diagram provides an overview of the entities, i.e., actors, tools, infrastructures, and systems involved in the process *to-be* and the relationships among them.

Figure 3: Example of a structure diagram

Figure 3 contains an example of a UML class diagram for a Farm Management Information System in the context of a cheese production process.

The complete case study can be downloaded here: [UML class diagram](#)

Legend

Explanation of symbols

Class: defines the core elements, i.e., actors and resources. It is represented by a box with a title label;

Operations: the operations are performed by a class interacting with another class;

Relations: connect classes and are expressed by arrows.

Types of relations

Direct association: connects two classes by means of an operation. The arrow is directed from the active class which starts the operation to the passive class that is the recipient. Arrows placed in both directions mean that the two classes are both active.

Aggregation: means that a class is part of another class. This type of relation can be used to represent technological systems and components.

Process diagrams

The process diagrams represent the detailed flow of both the process *before* and the process *after*. The overlap of the two representations allows comparisons between the process before and after the introduction of the digital solution.

Figure 4: Example of a process diagram

Figure 4 contains an example of a BPMN diagram for a Farm Management Information System in the context of a cheese production process. This example represents the agronomist's process *after* the introduction of the Farm Management Information System (process *to-be*).

The complete example containing multiple views from the perspective of multiple actors and the high-resolution images can be downloaded here: [Process before - BPMN](#) - [Process after - BPMN](#) - [Process overlap - BPMN](#).

An additional example of process diagrams for a Precision Irrigation System in the context of a fruit farm can be downloaded here:

[Process before - BPMN](#) - [Process after - BPMN](#) - [Process overlap - BPMN](#)

The model represents a single view of the global process.

Legend

Figure 2: Legend of BPMN symbols used

Explanation of symbols

Start event: the starting point of a process;

Start timer event: a start event containing a message and triggered by another process;

End event: the ending point of a process;

Task: an atomic activity within a process flow. It can be of different types: manual, service, send, receive;

Parallel gateway: used to create concurrent paths within a process flow; for a single execution of the process, the paths can be taken in parallel;

Exclusive gateway: used to create alternative paths within a process flow. For a single execution of the process, only one of the paths can be taken;

Pool: A pool represents a participant who takes part in a process. All actions performed by the participant are represented inside the same pool. If multiple participants are involved in a process, multiple pools are defined. Each pool has a start and end event.

Connection: link with arrows between tasks and/or pools. Connections between pools represent communication flows and are represented with dashed lines.

Text annotation: additional elements that provide further explanation.

Modelling software and templates

Diagrams can be created with any tool supporting the languages UML, BPMN and iStar.

Suggested tools

For UML and BPMN diagrams we recommend the use of software enabling the export of UML/XML and BPMN formats. Instead, iStar diagrams can be created with any graphical tool supporting the elements of the notation.

We suggest the following tools:

- iStar: LucidSpark <https://lucidspark.com/it>
- UML: StarUML <https://staruml.io/>
- BPMN: Camunda <https://camunda.com/>

Additional information and alternative solutions

iStar - In case you are interested in generating goal models in the original iStar notation, you can use the online tool piStar: <https://www.cin.ufpe.br/~jhcp/pistar/>.

UML - The evaluation version of StarUML (freely available) presents some limitations in file exporting, e.g., adding a watermark in SVG files. The pro version (license needed) allows the creation of BPMN (BPMN diagrams creation in StarUML has not been tested for our purposes).

BPMN - For fast development of the model you can use the online tool:

<https://demo.bpmn.io/s/start> The online tool presents limitations in the generation of the overlapping view.

Templates

Use the following templates as a starting point for the creation of your diagrams.

1. Goal diagram iStar: [View on Lucidspark](#) (create a copy of the template before editing)
2. Structure diagram UML: [Download .mdl template](#)
3. Process diagram BPMN: [Download .bpmn template](#)

Overview: questions to diagrams

This section provides a general overview of the information to be extracted from the **Living Lab Reports**. In the following, questions of the report are mapped to specific information that needs to be extracted, elaborated and associated with one or more diagrams.

Please note that the report may present inconsistencies and missing information that could result in information being displaced and the need for further iterations with the Living Lab.

Furthermore, as the report is the outcome of multiple data collection activities carried out in CODECS, it may contain additional information not strictly necessary for the models. Use this information as a support to better contextualise the process and abstract all the relevant information.

[DIGITAL SOLUTION]

- Information to extract: tech system, components, actors and preliminary process

DIAGRAMS → UML iStar BPMN

- Information to extract: goals

DIAGRAM → iStar

[ACTORS PROCESS AFTER]

- Information to extract: actors

DIAGRAMS → UML iStar BPMN

[RESOURCES PROCESS AFTER]

- Information to extract: resources

DIAGRAMS → UML iStar BPMN

[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]

- Information to extract: activities/tasks

DIAGRAMS → UML iStar BPMN

[RATIONALE]

- Information to extract: goals

DIAGRAMS → iStar

[ADVANTAGES]

- Information to extract: goals

DIAGRAMS → iStar

[ACTORS PROCESS BEFORE]

- Information to extract: added/removed actors, actors process before

DIAGRAM → BPMN

[RESOURCES PROCESS BEFORE]

- Information to extract: added/removed resources

DIAGRAM → BPMN

[ACTIVITIES PROCESS BEFORE]

- Information to extract: activities process before, actors process before

DIAGRAM → BPMN

Procedure

This section contains the procedure for creating the diagrams.

Goal diagram - iStar

Follow this procedure to create Goal diagrams in iStar notation.

1) Actors

- a) Select actors from **[ACTORS PROCESS AFTER]** and create an Actor boundary.
- b) Select technology from **[DIGITAL SOLUTION]** and create an Actor boundary (Technology boundary); possibly place it at the centre of the diagram.

2) Goals

- a) For each actor select goals list from: **[RATIONALE]** and **[ADVANTAGES]**;
- b) Classify and create goals. Place goals in *internal, actor-actor* or *actor-technology* positions. Express goals through a short sentence containing a verb (e.g., *optimise animal health; share data; support farmer*)

Example - Vet's goals

Report: *Integrating information managed by different actors, the farm management information system supports advisors in the management of their work ...; The vet accesses stats of farms productivity because they wants to enhance the productivity of the animals; ...information provided help to schedule future activities ...*

Vet's goals - Optimise animal production (Internal goal); Monitor animal health (Actor-actor goal); Optimise work management (Actor-technology goal)

3) Tasks

- a) For each actor - except for technology - select main activities relevant to strategic aspects from **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]** and abstract tasks. Place tasks inside the actor's boundaries.

Example - Vet's tasks

Report: The vet visits each farm monthly to monitor the health status of animals; During a visit, the vet scans the animal through the bluetooth tag scan and accesses the app to annotate data about animals because they wants to record relevant facts about animals;

Vet's tasks- Visit animals; Scan animals.

4) Tools

- a) Select technological resources from **[RESOURCES PROCESS AFTER]** and **[DIGITAL SOLUTION]**; create and place tools inside the actor's boundaries, possibly below the correspondent task.

NOTE: in selecting resources, consider digital tools and technological components used by the actor for performing a task. Try to associate each task with a tool.

Example - Vet's tools

Report: bluetooth tag scan in use by the vet for on field data access and data entry... During a visit, the vet scans the animal through the bluetooth tag scan...

Vet's tool- Pet scan bluetooth

5) Connections

- a) *Tool-task:* for each tool, add a link between the tool and its corresponding task with the arrow directed from the tool to the task.
- b) *Task-goal:* for each task - except for tasks in technology boundary - add a link between the task and its corresponding goal with the arrow directed from the task to the goal. **NOTE:** one task can be connected to multiple goals. Each goal in the actor boundary has to be linked at least to one task. Each task in the actor boundary has to be linked at least to one goal. Possibly, place the goals above the tasks.
- c) *Actor-actor goal:* for each actor-actor goal, add a link connecting the two actor boundaries and the goal. The arrow should be directed from the active actor, e.g., the actor performing actions to fulfil the goal, to the recipient actor. If the actors share the same goal, e.g., *communication exchange*, the arrow should be put in both directions.
- d) *Actor-technology goal:* for each actor-technology goal, add a link connecting the actor boundary to the technology boundary with the arrow directed from the actor to the technology.

6) Export and save

Export a high-quality image in PNG format and save the current session. If you produce

multiple versions of the diagram, add the version number on the filename. E.g.,
goal-diagram_V1.png

Structure diagram - UML

Follow this procedure to create structure diagrams in UML notation.

1) Technology

- a) Select the tech system from **[DIGITAL SOLUTION]** and represent it as a class.
- b) Identify components (hardware and software) of the tech system from **[DIGITAL SOLUTION]** and **[RESOURCES PROCESS AFTER]**; represent them as class and link with aggregation, (i.e., diamond).
- c) Add a blue background to the classes.

Example

Report: The digital solution consists of a farm management information system (FMIS) to store information about sheep and milk production...; the system integrates multiple web services providing additional data that are managed by the cheese factory...Bluetooth tag scan in use by the vet for on-field data access and data entry; server for data storage; technological devices compatible with the app (e.g., smartphone/tablet/desktop); cloud storage and FMIS software.

Technology class - System: FMIS class, components: app, web dashboard, pet scan bluetooth, management software.

2) Actors and resources

- a) Select actors from **[Question 4.1] ACTORS PROCESS AFTER** and resources – except for technological resources – from **[Question 4.2] RESOURCES PROCESS AFTER** and represent them as class.

NOTE: In selecting resources, prioritise the elements mentioned in **[Question 4.3] ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER**, in the focal action situation, problem statement and **[Question 6.1] TRANSITION**.

Example

Report: farmer; ...; sheep

Classes - Farmer, Sheep

3) Connections

- a) *Actors-technology//Actor-resource*: add a link between the classes based on **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]**. Add a label on the link with the action performed by the actor using the technology or resource. The arrow direction should go from the actor to the technology.
- b) *Actors-actor*: if actors have direct interactions, add a link between the actors based on **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]**. The arrow direction should go from the *active* actor to the *passive*. In case both actors are active e.g., information exchange activity, add arrows on both sides or omit arrows.

NOTE: All blocks in the diagram should be connected to other blocks. Balance the readability and completeness of the diagram and choose a limited number of connections.

Example

Report: Every day, after milking, the farmer accesses the web dashboard to record the amount of milk collected because wants to monitor the amount of milk produced; the vet annotates data about animals to record relevant facts about animals; the vet annotates animals feeding plan; the vet accesses the dashboard to see data shared with the agronomist...; the agronomist accesses the dashboard to see data shared with the vet;

Actors-technology connection: - Link from class *farmer* to class *web dashboard* with label *access data*

Actors-resources connection: - Link from class *farmer* to class *sheep* with label *milking*.

Arrow direction: from *farmer* to *sheep*.

Actors-actors connection: - Link from class *veterinary* to class *agronomist* with label information exchange. Arrow direction: *both*.

4) Export and save

Export an image in SVG format and save the file in the UML software format. If you produce multiple versions of the diagram, add the version number on the filename. E.g.,

structure-diagram_V1.svg

Process diagrams - BPMN

Follow this procedure to create process diagrams in BPMN notation.

Diagram 1: BPMN process after

1) Actor pools

- a) Select actors from **[ACTORS PROCESS AFTER]** and create a pool for each actor.
- b) Select technology in **[DIGITAL SOLUTION]** and create a pool.

In case the process is composed of more than two actors having multiple interactions, create a model for each actor with empty pools around referring to the other actors. This should enhance the readability of the diagrams. Example: The cheese-making process in the farm management information system example is composed of the following models: farmer, vet, agronomist, and cheese factory. [See the example on the farm management information system.](#)

2) Start/End process

- a) Add a start event and an end event inside each pool.
- b) Add a text annotation on the start event and indicate the frequency of the process: daily, weekly, every three minutes, etc.

3) Tasks

- a) Select the activities from **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]** and create a sequence of connected tasks inside each actor boundary and within the start and end event. Optionally assign a type to each task choosing among: manual, system, receive, send.

Example

Report: The agronomist accesses the FMIS dashboard to see stats of farms productivity, data shared with the vet and data synchronised from external databases (e.g. milk analysis) because they want to enhance the productivity of the animals.

Agronomist's task - access FMIS, analyse data, plan food ratios, update FMIS, schedule visits

4) Connections

- a) Identify send tasks and create a link starting from the send task to the corresponding recipient's receive task / pool. In case the send task triggers the beginning of the recipient's process, transform the start event of the recipient into a message start event and connect the send task to this event.
- b) Add a label on the dotted line resulting from the connection with the object of the activity.

Example

Report: The farmer plans a meeting with the agronomist for discussing the feeding plan...;

Agronomist's tasks - visit farm (task) - request animal information (send task directed to farmer pool) - annotate animal facts (receive task incoming from farmer pool)

5) Gateways

- a) Parallel gateways: from **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]** extract activities that are executed in parallel and place a parallel gateway before the first task executed to create multiple paths. Add a task or a sequence of tasks to each path. Repeat the gateway after the last tasks.
- b) Exclusive gateways: from **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]** extract activities that are executed optionally and place an exclusive gateway to create multiple paths. Add a task or a sequence of tasks to each path. Add a label on the gateway explaining the condition and add a label on each path explaining the verification of the condition. Repeat the gateway after the last tasks.

Example

Report: In case of a sanitary emergency, the farmer calls the vet because wants the animal to be visited; The vet receives monthly a notification from the FMIS to schedule visits to the farms; The vet visits each farm monthly to monitor the health status of animals;

Vet's parallel gateway - tasks path 1- access FMIS; schedule visit; tasks path 2- visit farms

Vet's exclusive gateway - label condition: is there an emergency? - condition verification: yes, path 1- evaluate farm request (receive task incoming from farmer pool) - schedule visit (send task directed to farmer pool); condition verification: no, path 2 - empty

6) Text annotations

- a) Add text annotations on tasks to express additional relevant information provided in **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER]**.

7) Export and save

Export a high-quality image in PNG format and save the file in the BPMN software format. If you produce multiple versions of the diagram, add the version number on the filename. E.g., *process-before-diagram_V1.png*

Diagram 2: BPMN process before

1) Actor pools

- a) Copy in a new file the model(s) created in **Diagram 1: BPMN process after**
- b) Select actors that were not part of the process before in **[ACTORS PROCESS BEFORE]** and delete their pools.
- c) Delete or edit the technology pool according to the info in **[SOLUTION]**.
- d) Select actors from **[PROCESS BEFORE]** that are not in **[PROCESS AFTER]** and create new pools. Add start and end events inside the pool.

2) Tasks, connections, gateways

- a) Select activities from **[ACTIVITIES PROCESS BEFORE]** and edit the pool of each actor with corresponding tasks, relationships, gateways and annotations following the instructions provided in **Diagram 1: BPMN process after**.

3) Export and save

Export a high-quality image in PNG format and save the file in the BPMN software format. If you produce multiple versions of the diagram, add the version number on the filename. E.g., *process-after-diagram_V1.png*

Diagram 3: BPMN processes overlap

Please consider the examples provided (i.e., [Process before - BPMN](#) - [Process after - BPMN](#) - [Process overlap - BPMN](#)) to understand how to create the overlapping view. In addition, download this BPMN source file with an example of overlap: [BPMN source overlap](#).

1) Actor pools

- a) Copy in a new file the model(s) created in **Diagram1: BPMN process before**.
- b) Paste in the new file the content created in **Diagram2: BPMN process after**. Place Diagram2 next to Diagram1 and compare the two processes.

2) Green elements

- a) Colour in green all the elements of **Diagram1** that do not change in **Diagram2**.

3) Red elements

- a) Colour in red all the elements of **Diagram1** that are no longer present in **Diagram2**.

4) Blue elements

- a) Copy-paste all the new elements from **Diagram2**, colour in blue and overlap to **Diagram1**.

5) Remove Diagram2

6) Export and save

Export a high-quality image in PNG format and save the file in the BPMN software format. If you produce multiple versions of the diagram, add the version number on the filename. E.g., *process-overlap-diagram_V1.png*